

OPTIMIZING NUTRITIONAL EFFICIENCY IN RUMINANTS THROUGH RUMEN BYPASS PROTEINS AND BYPASS FATS

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ABSTRACT

High-yielding animals need a larger percentage of nutrients in their diet that do not degrade in the rumen and instead provide the intestinally required amino acids. The efficiency of protein utilization is reduced when proteins are fermented in the rumen prior to enzymatic digestion. Feed ingredients that include proteins with a greater bypass value can be used to supply ruminants with bypass proteins. Supplementing with rumen-protected protein, fat, and vitamins increases immunity, lowers heat stress, and increases milk output. Therefore, using protected/by-pass dietary nutrients can be a potential technique for improving both the quality and quantity of animal production in order to supply dairy animals with precise and high-quality nutrition during times of high nutrient demand.

Keywords: Rumen, amino acids, peak yield, optimal production, microorganisms, metabolism

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